

WHAT DRIVES UNIVERSITY EMPLOYEES? A STUDY OF TEACHERS AND STAFF MOTIVATION IN VIETNAM

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Abstract:

Lecturers and staff are important resources in universities. Their work performance is closely related to work motivation. The motivation of lecturers and staff in the university is affected by many different factors. In this study, we focused on assessing the influence of 5 factors: income, co-worker relationship, development opportunities, working conditions and nature of work. The study was carried out on a sample of 163 subjects who are lecturers and staff of a public university in Vietnam. Methods of exploratory factor analysis EFA, linear regression analysis were used to test the research hypotheses. Research results showed that all 5 factors considered have a positive impact on the work motivation of lecturers and staff. In which, the income factor has the strongest influence. The results of this study provide data as a basis for building motivational strategies for lecturers and staff at universities in Vietnam.

Keywords: *affecting factors, working motivation, lecturers and staff, universities, Vietnam.*

INTRODUCTION

A university is a vocational education institution with the goal of training qualified and skilled workers to contribute to the development of society. The reputation and value of a university are determined by the quality of training, the quality of training is determined by the performance of the faculty and staff (Munyengabe et al., 2016; Luu, 2020). Many studies show that the performance of lecturers and staff in universities is related to many different factors, in which work motivation is one of the factors that have a great impact (Rowley et al., 1996;

Gokce, 2010; Ayeni, 2015; Hung, 2020). In order to ensure and improve

the working efficiency of lecturers and staff, contribute to improving the quality of education, and strengthen the reputation of the school, it is necessary to pay attention to the work motivation of lecturers and employees (Dung, 2015; Kotherja & Rapti, 2015). In order to do this, university administrators need to be aware of work motivation, factors affecting the work motivation of lecturers and staff, so as to develop policies and procedures for the management of the university. appropriate and effective motivation.

Work motivation is an issue that has been discussed quite early. Pinder (1998) defines the work motivation "as a group of energetic forces that come internally and externally aimed at human behavior by setting the duration, intensity and direction. According to Ryan & Deci (2000), motivation is the combination of the desire of a person and energy directed at achieving a goal It can be internal to include a sense of satisfaction and feelings of achievement or external that includes rewards, punishments Internal motivation comes from the person, from his personal activities which positively

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affects the behavior, performance and the benefits from it. Sharing the same view, Dung (2015) believes that labor motivation is the desire and voluntariness of employees to increase efforts towards achieving organizational goals. Most researchers believe that work motivation plays a very important role. Stee & Porter (1983) argues that work motivation is a factor that changes the way work is done. Work and behavior of staff. Motivation is the willingness to exert efforts to achieve the highest goals of the organization, provided that the organization must be able to satisfy some individual need (Robbins, 1993) or the motivation to motivate behavior which gives direction to behavior and emphasizes the tendency to persist (Bartol & Martin, 1998).

When discussing the factors affecting the work motivation of employees in general, Hackman & Oldham (1974) mentioned aspects of job design. Besides work, Crossman & Abou Zaki (2003) pointed out other factors such as salary, promotion, supervision and relationship with colleagues. Pink (2009) believes that intrinsic motivation is formed and developed based on the following three factors: autonomy; self-mastery; purpose. Kovach (1987) proposed a model of ten factors that create work motivation, including: interesting work, appreciation and praise for work done, feeling of being in on things, job security, good wages, opportunities for advancement and development, good working conditions, personal loyalty to employees, tactful discipline, sympathetic help with personal problems. Some authors have deeply explored the factors affecting the work motivation of teachers and lecturers. In his research, Rowley (1996) discussed environmental factors that impact on motivation including: approaches to financial rewards, the culture of teaching and higher education, the diversity of staff experience and roles, personal autonomy, and organizational structure. Sah's study (2016) discovered factors such as salary, exposure to the teaching profession, respect for the teaching profession, working environment, support in teaching activities, satisfaction. In the work. Sabra et al, (2018) showed that the first factor positively motivated the academic staff to teach was self-confidence, followed by choice of teaching staff for their profession. While, the first anxiety factor negatively influenced the motivation of the academic staff to teach was in classroom, by examination stress and rewards. According to İpek & Kanatlar (2018), teaching environment, the workplace, collegial relations, and students are factors affecting the motivation of lecturers. A number of studies by Vietnamese authors also show many different factors: factors of the direct working environment such as job characteristics, working environment at the faculty/subject (the fairness of direct leaders) and the classroom environment (fairness in student behavior) (Dung, 2015); career passion, teaching capacity, salary and benefits, training and promotion, social recognition (Ly & Nga; 2016); training, promotion, salary, bonus, welfare, working environment and atmosphere, working conditions, working mode, rest, motivation, working attitude (Dung, 2017); salary, benefits, superiors, colleagues, working conditions, nature of work, training and promotion (My, 2019); Work characteristics, Wage and welfare, Social recognition, Peer relationships, Training and promotion opportunities, Leader caring and Teacher–student interaction and student's attitude have positive effect on lecturers' work motivation (Tuan & Do, 2020); job characteristics and facilities, student body, income, promotion (Linh et al., 2022). These research results show that there are many different factors affecting the work motivation of employees, depending on the field and operating environment. In which, common factors are: salary and benefits, nature of work, working environment, co-worker relations, working conditions, development opportunities.

This study was conducted to explore the factors affecting the work motivation of employees in universities, thereby proposing some implications on governance, contributing to improving the quality of human resource management. in university in Vietnam.

RESEARCH METHODS

Scales

This study uses the proposed research model (Figure 1) with scales built on the basis of reference and inherits research results of the following authors: Kovach (1987), (2009), Sah (2016), İpek & Kanatlar (2018), Dung (2015), Dung (2017), My (2019).

The proposed research model includes 5 independent variables and 01 dependent variables, with a total of 30 observed variables: 6 observed variables measuring income; 5 observed variables measure co-worker relationship; 5 observed variables measure development opportunities; 5 observed variables measure working conditions; 5 observed variables measuring the nature of work; 4 observed variables measure the work motivation of lecturers and staff. (Refer to the details of the variables in the appendix of the article)

All observed variables are measured using a 5-level Likert scale: 1: Completely disagree; 2: Disagree; 3: Normal; 4: Agree; 5: Totally agree.

Diagram 1. Proposed research model

Hypothesis H1: Income has a positive impact on the work motivation of lecturers and staff.

Hypothesis H2: Co-worker relationship has a positive impact on the work motivation of lecturers and staff.

Hypothesis H3: Development opportunities have a positive impact on the work motivation of lecturers and staff.

Hypothesis H4: Working conditions have a positive impact on the work motivation of lecturers and staff.

Hypothesis H5: The nature of work has a positive impact on the work motivation of lecturers and staff.

The proposed regression model to test the hypothesis is as follows:

$$DL = \beta_1 TN + \beta_2 QH + \beta_3 CH + \beta_4 DK + \beta_5 TC$$

The dependent variable is the work motivation (DL) and the independent variables are the influencing factors such as Income (TN), Co-worker relationship (QH), Development opportunities (CH), Working conditions (DK). Registration, Nature of work (TC). $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$: Normalized regression coefficient in multivariable regression model.

Sample

The sample of this study was selected according to the population sampling method, including 200 subjects. Tabachnick & Fidell (1996) said that, for multivariate regression analysis, the minimum sample size should be calculated according to the formula $N \geq 50 + 8 \cdot m$ (m: number of independent variables). According to Trong & Ngoc (2008), the minimum sample size for a study is $N = n \cdot 5$ (n is the number of observed variables). Our study includes 6 variables with 30 observed variables, so the sample size of 200 subjects is satisfactory.

Data analysis

The topic uses SPSS 20.0 software to analyze data and solve research objectives: descriptive statistics; Cronbach's Alpha test to test the reliability of the scale; Bartlett test and KMO test to confirm the concordance of survey results with EFA exploratory factor analysis; EFA analysis, correlation analysis, linear regression analysis to confirm the correlation and influence of factors on the work motivation of lecturers and staff.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive statistics of the survey sample and variables

We conducted a survey of 200 subjects, but only 163 valid answer sheets, which can be used for statistical analysis. Specific characteristics of the research sample and variables are presented in the tables below:

Table 1. Statistics of survey sample characteristics

Characteristics		Number	Percent
Gender	<i>Female</i>	97	59.5
	<i>Male</i>	66	40.5
	Total	160	100
Job position	<i>Staff</i>	54	33.1
	<i>Lecturer</i>	109	66.9
	Total	160	100
Qualification	<i>Undergraduate level</i>	18	11.0
	<i>Bachelor's Degree</i>	22	13.5
	<i>Postgraduate level</i>	123	75.5
	Total	160	100

(Source: Results of actual survey data processing, 2022)

The survey sample of this study consisted of 59.5% male and 40.5% female. 66.9% are lecturers and 33.1% are staff. 75.5% have a postgraduate degree, 13.5% have a university degree and 11% have undergraduate level.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of variables

No.	Factors	Mean	SD
1	Income	3.34	.83
2	Co-worker relationship	3.77	.55
3	Development opportunities	3.36	.89
4	Working conditions	3.38	.71
5	Nature of work	3.21	.87
6	Work motivation	3.41	.88

(Source: Results of actual survey data processing, 2022)

According to the descriptive statistics in Table 2, all variables have mean > 3.0, showing that the respondents in the survey sample agree with the above variables.

Testing the reliability of the scales through Cronbach's Alpha coefficient

Analyze the reliability of the scales through Cronbach's Alpha coefficient to eliminate inappropriate variables. Nunnally & Burnstein (1994) suggested that variables with a total correlation coefficient of less than 0.3 will be excluded and a scale is said to be reliable when it has Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.6 or higher. According to Trong & Ngoc (2008), a scale with Cronbach's Alpha from 0.8 to 1 is a good scale, from 0.7 to 0.8 is usable.

Table 3. Cronbach's Alpha results of the scales

Observed variables	Coefficient of correlation of total variables	Cronbach's Alpha if the variable is removed
Cronbach's Alpha <i>Income</i> = 0,905		
TN1	0,693	0,895
TN2	0,641	0,903
TN3	0,882	0,868
TN4	0,724	0,891
TN5	0,811	0,877
TN6	0,693	0,895
Cronbach's Alpha <i>Co-worker relationship</i> = 0,880		
QH1	0,674	0,863

QH2	0,692	0,859
QH3	0,776	0,842
QH4	0,789	0,835
QH5	0,651	0,871
QH6	0,674	0,863
Cronbach's Alpha <i>Development opportunities</i> = 0,919		
CH1	0,823	0,895
CH2	0,826	0,894
CH3	0,818	0,896
CH4	0,746	0,910
CH5	0,751	0,909
Cronbach's Alpha <i>Working conditions</i> = 0,810		
DK1	0,767	0,728
DK2	0,737	0,729
DK3	0,552	0,786
DK4	0,493	0,804
DK5	0,490	0,809
Cronbach's Alpha <i>Nature of work</i> = 0,813		
TC1	0,639	0,765
TC2	0,657	0,760
TC3	0,573	0,785
TC4	0,533	0,796
TC5	0,607	0,775
Cronbach's Alpha <i>Work motivation</i> = 0,805		
DL1	0,665	0,739
DL2	0,550	0,798
DL3	0,536	0,794
DL4	0,758	0,686

(Source: Results of actual survey data processing, 2022)

The results of Cronbach's Alpha in Table 3 show that all observed variables have total correlation coefficients > 0.3 . Cronbach's Alpha of all scales is greater than 0.6. From this result, it can be confirmed that all observed variables are accepted and we put all the variables into factor analysis.

Exploratory factor analysis EFA

In order to confirm the agreement of survey results with EFA exploratory factor analysis, we performed KMO and Bartlett test, the results are as follows:

Table 4. KMO and Bartlett test results

Factors to be assessed	Table value	Compare
KMO coefficient	0.847	$0 < 0.881 < 1$
Sig value in Bartlett test	0.000	$0.000 < 0.05$

(Source: Results of actual survey data processing, 2022)

The analytical results in Table 4 show that the KMO coefficient = 0.847 ($0.5 < \text{KMO} < 1$) and the Bartlett test has a value of Sig = 0.00 (< 0.05). These data suggest that the survey results are suitable for EFA analysis.

Table 5. EFA results of factors

Observed variables	Component				
	TN	QH	CH	DK	TC
TN3	.865				
TN5	.795				
TN4	.753				
TN2	.657				
TN1	.651				
TN6	.608				
QH3		.798			
QH4		.784			
QH2		.733			
QH5		.645			
QH1		.615			
CH1			.834		
CH2			.830		
CH3			.736		
CH5			.712		
CH4			.687		
DK1				.869	
DK2				.845	
DK3				.621	
DK5				.564	
DK4				.533	

TC2					8	.76
TC1					2	.72
TC5					0	.57
TC4					7	.55
TC3					3	.49

(Source: Results of actual survey data processing, 2022)

The results of factor rotation in Table 5 show that all observed variables have loading coefficients > 0.5 and converge in 5 groups, corresponding to the proposed research model and there is no shift of any observed variables. Thus, through EFA analysis, there are 5 factors drawn:

- Factor *Income* (TN) includes observed variables: TN3, TN5, TN4, TN2, TN1, TN6.
- Factor of *Co-worker relationship* (QH) includes observed variables: QH3, QH4, QH2, QH5, QH1.
- Factor *Development opportunities* (CH) includes observed variables: CH1, CH2, CH3, CH5, CH4.
- Factor *Working conditions* (DK) includes observed variables: DK1, DK2, DK3, DK5, DK4.
- Factor of *Nature of work* (TC) includes observed variables: TC2, TC1, TC5, TC4, TC3.

Pearson's correlation analysis

Pearson correlation coefficient test is used to test the linear relationship between independent and dependent variables before regression analysis.

Table 6. Results of correlation analysis between variables

		TN	CH	QH	TC	DK	DL
TN	Pearson Correlation	1	0,091	0,026	0,046	0,000	0,476**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0,247	0,740	0,560	0,995	0,000
CH	Pearson Correlation		1	0,094	0,003	-0,011	0,233*
	Sig. (2-tailed)			0,231	0,967	0,885	0,003
QH	Pearson Correlation			1	-0,043	-0,072	0,130*
					0,360		

	Sig. (2-tailed)				0,587		0,099
TC	Pearson Correlation				1	-0,011	0,206*
	Sig. (2-tailed)					0,889	0,008
DK	Pearson Correlation					1	0,168*
	Sig. (2-tailed)						0,032
DL	Pearson Correlation						1
	Sig. (2-tailed)						

(Source: Results of actual survey data processing, 2022)

From the results of correlation analysis in Table 6, it can be seen that all dependent variables (TN, CH, QH, TC, DK) are linearly correlated with the independent variable (DL) (correlation coefficient > 0). and Sig < 0.05). With this result, we put all the variables into the regression analysis model.

Linear regression analysis

Multiple regression analysis with 5 independent variables: Income (TN), Colleague Relations (QH), Development Opportunities (CH), Working Conditions (DK), Job Nature (TC), and 01 dependent variable: Working motivation (DL).

Table 6. Results of Regression Analysis

Model	Standardized Coefficients (β)	t	Sig.	VIF
Constant	3.424		0.000	
Income	0.328	0.048	0.000	1.011
Development opportunities	0.138	0.048	0.006	1.017
Co-worker relationship	0.091	0.049	0.005	1.017
Nature of work	0.142	0.049	0.004	1.004
Working conditions	0.133	0.048	0.006	1.005
Hệ số Durbin- Watson:		1.935		

(Source: Results of actual survey data processing, 2022)

The regression results obtained the adjusted R² value of 0.321, so the regression model is suitable for the data set. 05 factors in the model influence/explain 32.1% of the change in work motivation of lecturers and staff, the remaining 67.9% are influenced by factors other than the model and random error.

According to the analysis results in Table 6, all variables have VIF < 2, showing that there is no multicollinearity in the model. Durbin-Watson coefficient = 1,935 is in the range of 1.0 to 3.0, so there is no autocorrelation between residuals in the model.

Based on the size of the normalized regression coefficient β , the level of impact from the strongest to the weakest of the independent variables on the dependent variable DL is: TN, TC, CH, DK, QH, respectively.

From the analysis results, we have a standardized regression equation between 5 factors and the dependent variable "Work motivation of lecturers and staff" as follows: DL = 0.328*TN+0.142*TC+0.138*CH +0.133*DK+0.091*QH

CONCLUSION

The results of the research on factors affecting the work motivation of lecturers and staff of the proposed research model are summarized in the following table:

Table 7. Summary of research results

Hypothesis	Stated	Expectations of impact	Conclusion	Level of impact
H1	Income has a positive impact on the work motivation of lecturers and staff	(+)	Accepted	0.328
H2	Co-worker relationship has a positive impact on the work motivation of lecturers and staff	(+)	Accepted	0.138

H3	Development opportunities have a positive impact on the work motivation of lecturers and staff	(+)	Accepted	0.091
H4	Working conditions have a positive impact on the work motivation of lecturers and staff	(+)	Accepted	0.142
H5	The nature of work has a positive impact on the work motivation of lecturers and staff	(+)	Accepted	0.133

(Source: Results of actual survey data processing, 2022)

From the results summarized and presented in Table 7, the following conclusions can be drawn: All five factors in the model have the same impact on the work motivation of lecturers and staff. This means that when income, co-worker relations, nature of work, working conditions or development opportunities change, it will lead to a change in work motivation in the direction of increasing or decreasing.

Among 05 factors: Income, Co-worker relations, Development opportunities, Nature of work, Working conditions, Income has the most influence, the remaining 04 factors have lower influence.

All 5 research hypotheses we proposed were initially accepted. This proves that the proposed research model is appropriate. However, in order to have a better overview of the factors affecting the work motivation of lecturers and staff, it is necessary to conduct other studies, considering factors other than this research model.

In order to improve the working motivation of lecturers and staff in the university, from the research results, we believe that education managers need to pay special attention and have appropriate policies to improve income for lecturers and staff, especially in the context of the current market economy. Besides, education managers also need to pay attention to improving working conditions, improving and developing relationships in the organization, creating development opportunities for lecturers and staff.

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